

Factors Of Buying And Selling Of Ijon Rice In Soko District Tuban Regency, Indonesia

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Abstract: *The agricultural sector in Soko sub-district, Tuban Regency is expected to increase income. With limited resources and economy, farmers only work on a plot of land. The level of knowledge, education, health is low and the uncertainty of harvest yields, making cultivators often get into debt. This paper aims to determine the cause of the sale and purchase of rice in ijol. To achieve this goal, the data collection method used interviews and documentation which were analyzed by qualitative methods. The main results of this paper are the lack of education and lack of knowledge of technology which results in a lack of knowledge of market prices and the inability of farmers to access their crops to larger markets, This causes farmers to sell their crops before harvest. As for other things, food needs and children's school fees are the reason farmers sell rice on a bondage basis to slashers.*

Keywords: *Buying and Selling Ijon, Rice, Farmers, Slashers*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Indonesian agricultural sector plays an important role in the national economy and is a source of community life. The important role of agriculture is shown by the fact that most people live and work in agriculture. Farmers are generally rural communities who have an important role in the behavior of farmers. Village farmers with low education, lack of capital and limited resources make them only able to work on a piece of land.

Indonesia's largest foreign exchange contributor comes from the agricultural sector. Most of Indonesian people's lives come from agriculture, especially rural communities, this makes farmers faced with efficient alternatives in utilizing limited resources. Farmers in lowland areas mostly choose to grow rice because of the short harvest period and fertile soil. Rice cultivators are certainly not only big farmers but also small farmers, this has an impact on the practice of buying and selling rice on a bond basis, small farmers with limited capital and slashers who require large yields but small farmers cannot fulfill it. Abdul Hariss (2013:36) argues that bondage is an agreement made to obtain future results from objects whose results are uncertain in the future.

Meeting basic needs is an economic activity carried out by people every day. The basic needs of some people such as small farmers are not necessarily met with their income, by means of debt one can cover other needs. Small farmers with low yields make them sell their crops on a bondage basis to the slasher, which is considered to be able to reduce costs and meet sudden needs. In Muhammad Budiyanto's study (2015) the factors that cause bonded trading are influenced by factors of meeting basic needs, seeking profit, lack of science and technology as well as cultural factors and referrals of groups or people.

As for research on bonded trading, where studies analyze the factors that influence bonded buying and selling (Endang Lestari, 2017), research that analyzes bonded sale and purchase of bananas according to sharia economics (Sarmini Lilis, 2018). From this research, various approaches were applied to research bond trading.

The results of the study are not much different, that the factors behind farmers in bonded trading on their harvests are due to the large economic needs with the need for clothing, food and school fees for children. This research is different from the studies above, which focus on Islamic law and economic factors. This research is related to the factors of buying and selling in bonded transactions.

There is a purpose in this study to find out the factors that cause the people of Sandingrowo Village, Soko Subdistrict, Tuban Regency to practice buying and selling in bonds. The benefits of this research are that it is expected to add related knowledge, and can be used as information and considerations in making rice farmers' decisions. Therefore, this study is very important to do because it can make farmers' information in making decisions in buying and selling bonds.

II. METHODS

This research uses the approach qualitative descriptive conducted in the field (field research) where the investigation of objective symptoms that occurred in the location for the preparation of scientific reports in order to answer the factors causing the sale and purchase of rice bonding. The research was conducted in a qualitative descriptive manner in order to describe the facts that occurred systematically and accurately in writing or verbally which were observed from a person's behavior. This study attempts to present the results of interviews with a comparison of existing literature.

This research is sourced from two types of related data sources, namely the types of primary and secondary data. Primary data generated from direct research at the location of the village of Sandingrowo, Kecamatan Soko of Tuban Regency. The secondary data sources were obtained from literature studies and data from the Sandingrowo village profile. In addition to the sanding rowo village profile data, farmers involved in bonded rice trading were used as data samples using purposive sampling and snowball techniques to add data sources that were lacking and did not meet the research information. Data collection is done by interview and documentation method is the process of obtaining information or data related to the research objectives. The method of documentation obtained is in oral form because the rice sale and purchase contract in a bonded manner is not written.

Inductive qualitative research is used in building new general concepts, insights and understandings. With inductive thinking patterns, researchers can see the factors regarding the sale and purchase of rice bonds. This can be known, by obtaining the necessary information and data from related books and records. Miles and Huberman (Sugiyono 2011:91) state that there are 3 (three) steps in data analysis, namely: 1) Data Reduction 2) Data Display 3) Data Verification.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sandingrowo Village, Soko District, Tuban Regency, East Java, with an area of 186,193 hectares, with most of the population working as small farmers. Based on the results in the field, the practice of buying and selling rice on a bonded basis, the researchers conducted interviews with informants regarding this matter. The following are the results of interviews with village officials regarding the factors in the occurrence of bonded trading:

"Factors that cause people to continue to buy and sell bonds other than because it has become a tradition are due to urgent needs such as food needs, school children's expenses that cannot be postponed.(Interview with village officials)

Furthermore, related to other factors causing bonded trading, farmers stated:

"Because to pay debts to the penebas because in the production process there is a lack of capital so borrowing from the penebas is easier to process than to financial institutions or banks because he

thinks it will be complicated and the process takes a long time and requires collateral so that it becomes difficult for him to sell his rice to farmers. slash by bondage" (Interview with farmer)

Other farmers revealed other reasons for selling their crops in bonds
"Buying and selling rice bondage due to urgent needs such as food needs, school fees for children"(Interview with other farmers)

Based on the results of the interview, it can be stated that the reason they sell on a bond basis is because of the tradition that is usually done by farmers, the large capital for harvesting rice is also an incentive for farmers to sell their harvests before the time is right. The reason for the urgent need is the factor that causes small farmers to sell their crops on a bondage basis.

Lack of knowledge and low yields make it difficult to access farmers' market information. The low level of education which results in knowledge of technology makes them not aware of the latest market prices that have been set by the agricultural sector, so that farmers only know prices from middlemen. Most of the parties want goods in large quantities, but the farmers cannot afford it, with this the farmers think that selling their crops in bonded bonds is more practical than having to wait for harvest time.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

That from the results of research on the factors causing the buying and selling of rice bonds in the village of Sandingrowo, it can be concluded that the traditions of the people who are accustomed to the practice of buying and selling bonded rice, The urgent need for money, both to meet the needs of food, clothing, shelter, school fees that cannot be postponed any longer makes rice farmers sell their crops using a bonded system, thus making them feel benefited even though in practice there may be the possibility of experiencing losses that are not previously estimated, as well as the views of those who think that by buying and selling bonds, it will minimize time and is very practical. This is what ultimately causes the tradition of buying and selling bonds to persist in Sandingrowo Village, Soko District, Tuban Regency.

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